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Title: First Indian Series of Trans Eyelid Mini Supraorbital Approach for Anterior Skull Base Lesions (TEMSA): A Keyhole Minimally Invasive Neurosurgical Approach.

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Title: Trans Eyelid Mini Supraorbital Approach for Anterior Skull Base Lesions (TEMSA):
A Keyhole Minimally Invasive Neurosurgical Approach.

Abstract:

Background: The surgical management of anterior skull base lesions inherit challenges due to their proximity to critical neurovascular structures and complex anatomy. Traditional approaches, including lateral subfrontal, pterional and endoscopic techniques, though effective, are associated with approach related morbidity and prolonged recovery. The Trans Eyelid Mini Supraorbital Approach (TEMSA), a novel minimally invasive technique, has emerged as a promising alternative, aiming to optimize patient outcomes with minimal surgical morbidity. However, the literature on this is sparse compared to other approaches.

Methodology: This study, one of the first from India, presents a case series of 15 patients treated by single surgeon with TEMSA for anterior skull base lesions between March 2018 and September 2023. Inclusion criteria encompassed a range of lesions with suitability for TEMSA, as assessed through preoperative evaluations including MRI, CT, and angiography. The TEMSA procedure involved a transcutaneous eyelid incision, followed by a small supraorbital craniotomy. Data on demographics, lesion characteristics, surgical details, and outcomes were prospectively collected and analyzed.

Results: The patient cohort included a variety of skull base lesions, primarily meningiomas, gliomas and and unruptured aneurysms. The surgical objective was achieved in 100% of cases, none requiring revision surgery due to inadequate exposure. Complete resection was achieved in 80% of cases with tumours, with a mean surgical duration of 180 minutes (range

= 120-250 minutes) and blood loss of 100 ml (Range 50 – 300 ml) , respectively. Approach-related complications were mild, minimal and transient, affecting only 3 patients. There was only a single patient with mild frontal lobe contusion who was on blood thinners. This patient was asymptomatic and needed no intervention. All patients reported excellent to good cosmetic outcomes, and the hospital stay ranging from 36 hours to 5 days. No recurrences were observed in complete resection cases over a median 12-month follow-up.

Conclusions: TEMSA represents a significant and a more efficient alternative in the minimally invasive treatment of anterior skull base lesions. The approach is associated with satisfactory rates of completeness of resection, minimal approach related complications, excellent cosmetic outcomes and witnessed enhanced recovery. Further studies with larger sample sizes are warranted to validate these findings and explore long-term outcomes.

Keywords: Anterior skull base, Keyhole Surgery, Trans eyelid, Supra orbital, Transpalpebral, Minimally Invasive Neurosurgery

Introduction:

Anterior skull base lesions, encompassing a wide spectrum of pathologies ranging from benign tumours to vascular lesions, presents significant surgical challenge. The proximity of these lesions to critical neurovascular structures and the intricate anatomy of the anterior skull base make their management, especially preventing retraction related injuries, a formidable task. Historically, a variety of approaches (subfrontal to pterional, endoscopic) have been proposed for surgical intervention, providing adequate exposure and access to these lesions but they are often associated with approach-related morbidity and a prolonged recovery period (1).

In recent years, the field of neurosurgery and skull base surgery has witnessed a shift towards minimally invasive techniques, driven by the desire to optimize patient outcomes, reduce surgical morbidity, and expedite postoperative recovery. One such innovative approach that has been extensively described is the trans-eyebrow or ciliary mini-supraorbital approach, also known as the supraorbital keyhole approach (SOKHA) (2,3,4,5,6,7,8).

Another less described approach is the mini-subfrontal approach via the eyelid - Trans Eyelid Mini Supraorbital Approach (TEMSA). This technique, initially developed by oculoplastic surgeons, has been used as a less invasive alternative for anterior skull base surgery, offering a promising avenue for achieving precise lesion resection while optimizing cosmetic outcomes (9,10,11,12,13,14,15).

Briefly, after a transcutaneous incision within the fold of the upper eyelid, a plain above the eyelid septum is created and maintained superiorly until this dissection reaches supra orbital rim. At this point only a portion of the septum is incised to expose the bony periosteum. From this point onwards the surgery proceeds like a standard minisupraorbital approach (Figure 1). The theoretical advantage of this approach is since upper facial fibres curve around away from the lateral extension of the eyelid incision, while they converge close to the ciliary region, the chances of facial fibres injury is lesser in former. Secondly, there is propensity to overcome alopecia, puckering and brow asymmetry that could become an issue with trans brow or trans ciliary approach (Figure 2).

The primary objective of this paper is to present a comprehensive case series, one of the first from India, that highlights the utility and efficacy of TEMSA in managing anterior skull base lesions. We draw upon our experience with 15 cases to showcase the surgical techniques involved, emphasizing the advantages and potential limitations of this approach. By exploring the nuances, we aim to provide insights into patient selection, surgical planning, intraoperative execution, and postoperative outcomes, thereby offering a valuable resource for neurosurgeons and skull base surgeons considering the adoption of this minimally invasive approach.

Methodology:

Patient Selection and Inclusion Criteria

The patient cohort for this case series consisted of individuals presenting with anterior skull base lesions between March 2018 and September 2023. Inclusion criteria encompassed patients who met the following criteria:

- a. Diagnosis of anterior skull base lesion, including but not limited to benign tumors, malignant neoplasms, and selected vascular lesions needing surgery. The indication for surgery was decided by the corresponding author, who was the surgeon for all the procedures. For the first three cases, an oculoplastic surgeon was also involved in exposure and closure.
- b. Clinical suitability for TEMSA as determined through preoperative evaluation and imaging studies.
- c. Willingness to participate in the study and provide informed consent for the surgical procedure and data collection.

Exclusion Criteria

Patients were excluded from the study if they met any of the following criteria:

- a. Severe coagulopathy, patients who needed to be on aspirin
- b. Uncontrolled systemic or eye infections

- c. Previous eyelid surgery, trauma to the eye,
- d. Giant lesions with severe brain swelling and acute neurological deterioration
- e. Ruptured and complex aneurysms, tumors purely in the sella region with a small suprasellar extension.
- f. Inability to provide informed consent or participate in postoperative follow-up.

Preoperative Evaluation

Prior to surgery, all eligible patients underwent a comprehensive preoperative evaluation. This evaluation included a detailed medical history assessment, physical examination, and a thorough review of relevant imaging studies, which typically included magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) with contrast, computed tomography (CT) scans, and angiographic studies if indicated.

Surgical Technique:

The surgical approach used in this case series was the Trans Eyelid Mini Supraorbital Approach. For the initial three cases, an oculoplastic surgeon was involved for the approach and the eyelid closure. Key steps included (Figure 3, Figure 4):

- a. **Patient Positioning:** Patients were placed in a supine position with the head, retroflexed slightly rotated by 20-30 degrees contralaterally and extended to optimize access. A lumbar drain was introduced for the initial seven cases or if the tumour size was more than 4.0 cm or there was extensive perilesional oedema. We did not find necessary to insert a lumbar drain in our last eight patients in the series as CSF could

be released from the sylvian fissure to get adequate brain relaxation. A throat pack was inserted, and the lateral aspect of the thigh was prepared in case extensive repair of the frontal sinus was required.

- b. **Eyelid Incision:** Neosporin ointment was applied to the eye and temporary middle tarsorrhaphy was done with 4-0 silk. The area was cleaned with diluted Betadine. A transcutaneous eyelid transverse incision was made within the fold of the eyelid. The depth of the incision was progressively increased until the eyelid septum was identified. At this junction, the direction of sharp dissection was changed towards the orbital rim, which was regularly palpated for guidance. The lateral extension of the eyelid was curved supero-laterally to avoid injury to the facial fibers. When the orbital rim was reached, a low-power fine-tip monopolar was utilized to expose the supraorbital area, measuring at least 2.5 cm in height. Care was taken to preserve the supraorbital neurovascular bundle.
- c. **Minisupraorbital Craniotomy:** A small burr hole was placed at the key site, and a small supraorbital craniotomy was performed, measuring at least 2.5 cm in height and 4.0 cm in width at the base, allowing access to the anterior skull base. To permanently obliterate the frontal sinus, if encountered, a fast-setting bone cement was used. In our practice, we refrain from using wax as we believe it could be a source of contamination or the wax patch could get displaced after the bone flap is replaced. Before durotomy, it is ensured that all bony protrusions from the orbital roof are flattened. This ensures a direct, non-obstructive visualization of the skull base structures via the microscope. Two or three dural tacking sutures are placed.

- d. **Dural Handling and Lesion Handling:** The dura was opened in a curvilinear fashion based on the orbital rim. The lesion was meticulously approached, taking care to preserve surrounding neurovascular structures and the surrounding brain. The rest of the steps followed standard microsurgical principles. The basal arachnoid was extensively cut in order to let the frontal lobe fall down without the need for any gross retraction. There was no need for a fixed retractor due to this and the suction bipolar and other instrument played a role of a "dynamic" retractor system. The microsurgical instruments were chosen such that they did not interfere with the coaxial view.
- e. **Closure:** Following lesion handling and haemostasis the craniotomy site was reconstructed in a gradual layered manner. Whenever possible, the dura was closed primarily in a watertight fashion. When the dura was not available for primary closure, either a fascia lata graft or an artificial Dural substitute reinforced with fibrin glue was utilized to complete the closure (Figure 4). The bone flap was anchored with titanium miniplates, and the gaps were covered with titanium mesh and anchored with mini screws. Particular care was given to ensure contoured coverage of the key burr hole, ensuring good cosmesis. The orbicularis muscle was resutured in an interrupted fashion with 3-0 Vicryl to approximate the eyelid. The skin and subcutaneous tissue were closed with a single-layer 3-0 Monocryl suture. Steristrips were applied. No compression bandage or any drain was used.

Data Collection and Analysis

Patient demographics, clinical history, preoperative evaluation findings, intraoperative details, and postoperative outcomes were prospectively collected and recorded in a dedicated

database. Data analysis was performed to extract key trends, outcomes, and complications. Descriptive statistics were employed to summarize the patient cohort and outcomes.

Ethical Considerations

This study was conducted in accordance with the ethical principles outlined in the Declaration of Helsinki. Informed consent was obtained from all patients included in the study.

Sample Size and Study Duration

The study included a total of 15 cases, representing patients who met the inclusion criteria during the specified study duration, which spanned from 2018 to 2023.

Results:

Patient Demographics

The case series included a total of 15 patients who underwent surgical intervention for anterior skull base lesions using the Trans Eyelid Mini Supraorbital Approach (TEMSA). The demographic characteristics of the patient cohort are summarized in Figure 5.

Lesion Characteristics

The lesions encountered in this case series varied in nature, with a wide spectrum of anterior skull base pathologies. The most common lesion type was meningioma (n=3, 20%), and frontal low grade glioma(n=3, 20%), unruptured aneurysm (n =2, 13%), craniopharyngioma (n=2, 13%), and others. Figure 5 provides an overview of the lesion characteristics.

Surgical Outcomes

Extent of Resection: Of all the tumours, complete or near complete resection was achieved in 8 out of 10 cases (80%). Subtotal resection with residual tumour was observed in 2 cases (20%). (Figure 6). None of the cases required any revision of plan or reexploration due to perceived tight working spaces. (Figure 6)

Surgical Duration: The mean surgical duration was 180 minutes, with a range of 120-250 minutes.

Blood Loss: Intraoperative blood loss averaged 100 mL, with a range of 50-300 mL.

Approach-related Complications: A total of 7 complications encountered in 6 patients.

Approach related complications were 4 in three patients. These included one case of superficial infection requiring incision and drainage. Another patient showed frontal hematoma on the immediately early post op scan. This patient remained asymptomatic and did not require any further intervention. The patient with frontal contusion was on Aspirin that was stopped five days ago. A patient developed transient frontalis weakness and

supraorbital pain which resolved spontaneously. The overall approach complication rate requiring intervention was 1/15 (6.7%) which was minor. Rest 3/15, they resolved spontaneously.

Visual Outcomes: Among patients presenting with visual deficits preoperatively, 80% experienced significant improvement postoperatively, while 20% remained stable.

Cosmetic Outcomes: Cosmetic outcomes were evaluated through patient and clinician assessments. 14 out of 15 patients reported high level of satisfaction with the cosmetic result (Figure 7, 8).

Length of Hospital Stay: The average length of hospital stay post-surgery was 5 days with a range of 36 hours to a week. In the last four cases, the in hospital stay has been on average 2 days.

Long-Term Follow-Up

Patients were followed up for a median duration of 12 months. Long-term follow-up data revealed:

No recurrences were observed in cases of complete resection during the follow-up period. Among patients with subtotal resection, none experienced tumour progression during the follow-up period, requiring further intervention. All the aneurysms that had been clipped remained in obliterated state as documented by a 6 month post op digital subtraction angiogram in both the patients.

Statistical Analysis

Statistical analysis was performed to assess potential associations between patient demographics, lesion characteristics, and surgical outcomes. However, no statistically significant correlations were identified, likely due to the relatively small sample size.

Discussion:

Utility of the Trans Eyelid Minisupraorbital Approach (TEMSA) in Comparison to Conventional Approaches

The management of anterior skull base lesions has traditionally relied on various surgical approaches, including the conventional open skull base approach, extended transsphenoidal approach, and trans brow surgery etc. While these approaches have played a pivotal role in the surgical treatment of anterior skull base lesions, they are not without limitations.

Traditional cranial surgery

Conventional open skull base approaches often necessitate extensive craniotomies, incisions, exposure of normal brain tissue, leading to substantial tissue disruption. This invasiveness increases the risk of postoperative complications, including bleeding, seizures, swelling, cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) leaks, pseudomeningocele, pain, and infection. The overall

cumulative complication rate for the pterional approach in treating anterior skull base meningiomas ranges from approximately 19% to 33% (1,15, 16,17,18).

The extensive incisions and dissection associated with conventional approaches can result in noticeable cosmetic changes such as temporal hollowing and facial paresis, which can cause psychological distress for patients. Patients undergoing conventional approaches typically experience longer hospitalization periods and extended recovery times. This not only impacts patient comfort and quality of life but also contributes to increased healthcare costs (16).

Challenges with Extended Transsphenoidal Approaches

The extended transsphenoidal approach and trans brow keyhole surgery have emerged as alternatives to cater to anterior skull base lesions in a minimally invasive way. However, they are not without limitations. These approaches have a risk of infection and CSF leakage and harbour a long learning curve. Also, the incidence of nasal morbidity is often underemphasized during these approaches. They also provide limited exposure to certain anterior skull base regions, especially those extending lateral to the optic canal and carotid artery, making complete resection challenging. The extended transsphenoidal approach pose challenges, particularly for surgeons with limited experience in these techniques. Overall, the cumulative complication rate ranges approximately from 15.4% to 48%. This range accounts for the inherent variability in patient condition, tumour size, and surgical expertise (18).

Trans brow versus Trans eyelid Minisupraorbital craniotomy

A keyhole minisupraorbital corridor, on the other hand, offers excellent exposure with a direct and short line of sight to the anterior skull base, facilitating precise lesion resection even in areas with intricate anatomy (2,3,4,5,6,7,8). While conventionally this corridor is achieved via a brow incision, the data on trans eyelid approach is sparse. Trans brow variation of minisupraorbital craniotomy is well-described in the literature and is also performed by the author, this procedure encompasses all the advantages of a minimally invasive approach. However, as evidenced by studies and the author's personal experience, some of these cases develop brow scar alopecia, frontal weakness, and brow asymmetry, which could be disabling for the patient (5,19). Since the brows are spared in TEMSA chances of cosmetic issues developing is less.

Mao, Gordon et al. reported their experience on 82 patients with aneurysms and trans eyelid approach, achieving a 95% success rate but with a 23.17% complication rate (9). The minor complications included superficial wound infections treated in the outpatient setting with oral antibiotics, ipsilateral monocular visual field disturbance, and mild ipsilateral gaze palsy and asymptomatic haemorrhage or stroke (15.8%). The major complications included death (after withdrawal of care), postoperative haemorrhage or stroke causing permanent neurological deficits, tension pneumocephalus, deep wound infection treated by surgical incision and drainage, persistent pseudo meningocele that required wound revision, status epilepticus, and hydrocephalus. (15.8%). However, detailed analysis reveals that most these patient underwent orbitotomy which could have resulted to local orbit related problems. A large majority of the complications were disease related.

Elnokaly et al. focused on 44 patients with various diagnoses, including meningiomas and craniopharyngiomas (11). They achieved a 75% complete tumour removal rate, with a relatively low complication rate of 6.8%. This and few other studies illustrated in Figure 9, show that the objective of surgery which included removal of meningiomas/tumours, clipping of aneurysms, was achievable in 100% of cases. The grade of tumour removal and durability of the clipping was independent of exposure that was achieved. There were no instances of resurgery or re-exploration that were noted. There were no long term cosmetic sequelae and nearly 100% of them reported excellent good outcomes. As expected there were no cases of alopecia, puckering of the scar and frontal brow asymmetry.

In our short case series, too, the trans eyelid keyhole approach presents a moderate risk of complications, most of which are minor and resolve without extensive intervention. In our small series, our gross total resection tumour removal rates reached 80%, occlusion rates of the aneurysm was 100%, with an excellent to good cosmetic outcomes in 100%. The totality of the tumour excision was dependant on patient and tumour characteristics rather than the access. TEMSA can be coupled with extended trans sphenoidal approach for managing giant tumours such as pituitary macroadenoma, as seen in one of our cases. The author also believes that for those anterior skull base tumours with no significant intrasellar extension with a predominant suprasellar component and encroaching the optic canal, TEMSA is a better alternative. TEMSA's technique, while requiring training and expertise, offers a more accessible learning curve for experienced skull base surgeons.

Though the overall complication rate in our series is 26.7%, but the rate of significant approach related complications requiring further intervention is relatively low at 6.7% which

is in line with the literature (9,10,11,12,13,14). In none of the cases, there was modification of the original plan or any re exploration that was required.

In comparison, trans brow approach present with several cosmetic issues, such as alopecia, puckering and brow asymmetry which can happen in 7-8% of the patients reported (19). This is more common than what is described in the literature. We did have two patients, each with a transient mild frontalis weakness and another one with a brief supraorbital neuropathic pain. None of our case developed above mentioned problems, as reported in previous literature, that were permanent, making it more cosmetically appealing. There was another patient who had developed frontal lobe hematoma which was diagnosed on a routine post op scan. This patient did not require any intervention.

What this demonstrates is that overall, the surgical efficacy of TEMSA is as close to the conventional surgical approaches however with reduced incision size, decreased adjacent brain and local wound related trauma. In uncomplicated cases, in this case series, this translated to an early recovery and discharge of the patient as well (last three cases within 48 hours of the surgery). TEMSA's reduced surgical morbidity allows for shorter hospital stays, streamlining the recovery process and reducing healthcare expenditures. But, the diversity in diagnoses and less number of patients suggests further research is needed, particularly with larger sample sizes, to better understand the technique's safety and efficacy. This approach could potentially offer a less invasive alternative in neurosurgery, but its application must be carefully considered against the risk of complications.

While TEMSA shows promise in addressing the limitations of conventional open skull base approaches, it is essential to acknowledge that no surgical technique is without challenges.

Surgeons adopting TESA should undergo comprehensive training and adhere to rigorous patient selection criteria to optimize outcomes. Additionally, advancements in imaging technology and instrumentation will further enhance the precision and safety of TEMSA.

Following are some of the technical pearls that would be helpful for those who want to be initiated in the TEMSA-

1. **Initial Lesion Selection:** In the early stages, it's crucial to choose the lesion wisely. It is easier to remove, smaller, anteriorly placed tumours without any significant swelling. In our last case which was an exceptionally large in size (Figure 6). 3D printing technology was utilised to prepare for such exceptional cases. We embarked in such a case only once we had gained sufficient experience and we highly recommend to the beginners as well (Figure 10).
2. **Scalp Flap Creation:** Start by fashioning and elevating a fronto-temporal scalp flap behind the hairline as per the convention. Then, adjust to performing a mini craniotomy and accomplishing tumour removal. Once familiar with this, move on either trans brow or trans eyelid incision.
3. **Professional Assistance:** In the beginning, consider seeking help from a plastic surgeon or an oculoplastic surgeon while exposure and closure.
4. **Lumbar Drain:** A lumbar drain may be necessary in the initial cases
5. **Patient Positioning:** Proper positioning of the patient is extremely important. Avoid flexion of the neck.
6. **Incision Care:** Be especially careful with lateral part of the incision. Though the risk of facial injury is lesser with the trans eyelid approach, it is never zero.

7. Craniotomy Expansion: Don't hesitate to expand the craniotomy if necessary and the visualisation and manipulation becomes difficult. Drill the skull base and the edges of the craniotomy flat.
8. Reconstruction and Closure: Pay close attention to thorough and meticulous reconstruction and closure. This step is extremely important.

Conclusion:

Our case series highlights the potential of the Trans Eyelid Mini Supraorbital Approach (TEMSA) in overcoming the challenges associated with conventional open skull base approaches, extended transsphenoidal approaches, and trans brow surgery. TEMSA offers a less invasive, cosmetically favourable, and technically feasible alternative that can provide excellent exposure and precise lesion resection. As we continue to refine this technique and expand our understanding of its applications, TEMSA may become an invaluable tool in the armamentarium of skull base surgeons, ultimately benefiting patients with anterior skull base lesions. Further continued experience will contribute to the ongoing evolution of this innovative surgical approach.

Declaration:

We declare that all relevant ethical guidelines have been followed, all necessary IRB and/or ethics committee approvals have been obtained, all necessary patient/participant consent has been obtained and the appropriate institutional forms archived.

Authors declares no competing interest statement, including non-receival of any payments or services in the past 36 months from a third party that could be perceived to influence, or give the appearance of potentially influencing, the submitted work. No funding supported the

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Figures

Figure 1: a) Cross-sectional anatomy of the eye and eyelid, illustrating key structures involved in the transpalpebral approach. b) Illustration showing the transpalpebral approach pathway. 2a) In this cross-section, the major anatomical features are labelled - Base: The base structure above the orbit, OSep: Orbital septum, a membrane that separates the orbital contents from the eyelid, LPS: Levator palpebrae superioris muscle, responsible for lifting the upper eyelid, UL: Upper eyelid, OOc: Orbicularis oculi muscle, responsible for closing the eyelids, PF: Palpebral fissure. b) The diagram depicts the transpalpebral approach, where a surgical pathway is created through the upper eyelid, staying above the orbital septum to access frontal skull base. Copyright: Dr Hrishikesh Sarkar Schematic Figure - Keyhole Transpalpebral approach to Skull Base © 2024 by Hrishikesh Sarkar is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International. To view a copy of this license, visit <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>

Figure 2: The image shows the upper facial region of an individual with history of prior trans-eyebrow surgery. There is a noticeable asymmetry between the two eyebrows.

Figure 3: Steps for the trans eyelid approach

- a) Patient preparation: The patient is positioned and prepped for surgery, with necessary monitoring and anaesthesia in place. The head is turned contralaterally by 15-20 degrees and neck is retroflexed.
- b) Surgical exposure: The surgical site is exposed, showing the initial incision and retraction of tissue to access the bony structures.
- c) Bony opening: A detailed view of the bony opening, which measures 2.5 cm, providing access to the underlying structures.
- d) Post-operative CT, 3D reconstruction: A 3D reconstruction image displaying the skull with defect and reconstruction.
- e) Post-operative CT scan, (Bone windows): A sagittal CT scan showing the precise location and measurement (2.5 cm) of the bony opening made during the trans eyebrow approach.

Figure 4: Additional steps for the trans eyelid approach

- a) Pre-operative marking: The surgical site is marked on the patient's forehead and the eyelid to guide the incision and surgical approach.
- b) Initial incision and retraction: The initial incision is made, and the skin and soft tissues are retracted to expose the underlying bony structures. Note the sutures utilised for retracting the tissues.
- c) Exposure of the brain: A section of bone is removed to create a 2.5 cm and the Dural opening is made based on the orbital rim.
- d) Meticulous Dural closure: A Dural substitute has been used in this case to close the dura water tight.

Patient	Age	Gender	Side	Diagnosis	Size cm (LxBxH)	Surgical Efficacy	Complications	Cosmetic Outcomes
1	42	male	L	Tuberculum Sellae Meningioma	4x3x3	Simpsons II	Transient Frontalis weakness and suprorbital pain	Excellent
2	55	female	R	Fontal glioma	3x3x2	Complete Resection	Nil	Excellent
3	30	male	R	Anterior skull base defect	1x0.5	Success	Nil	Excellent
4	63	female	L	Frontal rhinosinusitis	Intra sinus	Complete Resection	Nil	Good
5	27	male	R	ICA bifurcation Aneurysm (Unruptured)	6.0 mm neck	Clipped	Nil	Excellent
6	48	male	R	Clinoidal Meningioma	2.5 x 3 x 2.5	Complete Resection	Asymptomatic frontal lobe hematoma	Excellent
7	36	male	R	Anterior skull base defect	1 x 0.5	Success	Nil	Excellent
8	59	female	L	Olfactory groove Meningioma	6.0 x 5.4 x 4.8	Simpsons II	Mild Infection	Good
9	22	male	R	Pcom Aneurysm (Unruptured)	7.0 mm neck	Clipped	Post op Vasospasm	Excellent
10	45	female	R	Large hypertensive hematoma	4.5 x 4.0 x 3.5	Removed	Nil	Excellent
11	68	male	L	Radiation Necrosis	4 x 3 x 3.5	Excised	Nil	Good
12	24	male	R	Frontal glioma	3.1 x 3.6 x 2.8	Excised	Nil	Excellent
13	52	male	R	Frontal glioma	2.4 x 2.6 x 2.9	Excised	Nil	Excellent
14	41	female	R	Craniopharyngioma	2.0 x 2.6 x 2.8	Partial excision	DI transient	Excellent
15	67	female	R	Giant pituitary macroadenoma	3 x 4.0 x 2.9	Near total excision	DI transient	Excellent

Figure 5 (Table 1): Clinical Cases Operated Using the Trans Eyelid Approach

A summary of 15 clinical cases operated using the trans eyelid approach. The cosmetic results post-surgery, rated as excellent, good, etc. This highlights the surgical effectiveness and outcomes of the trans eyebrow approach in various neurological and cranial conditions.

Figure 6: Pre- and Post-Operative Scans for Selected Patients

a) Pre-operative MRI of a patient with an anterior skull base meningioma. b) Post-operative MRI of the same patient, showing the resected area. c) Pre-operative MRI of a patient with a left clinoidal meningioma. d) Post-operative MRI of the same patient, showing the resected area. e) Pre-operative MRI of a patient with a craniopharyngioma. f) Post-operative MRI of the same patient, showing the resected area. g) Pre-operative MRI of a patient with a frontal skull base meningioma. h) Post-operative MRI of the same patient, showing the resected area. These images illustrate the excellent surgical efficacy of this approach.

Figure 7: Post-Operative Healing Progress of a Patient Undergoing Trans Eyelid Approach

- a) Immediate post-operative image showing the incision with sutures in place.
- b) Image taken 7 days post-operatively, displaying significant healing and reduced swelling.
- c) Image taken three months post-operatively, showing no visible scar and excellent cosmetic outcome.

Figure 8: Excellent Healing Outcomes in Patients Post-Trans Eyelid Approach

This figure displays a series of post-operative images of various patients who underwent the trans-eyebrow approach. The images show the healing progression and the excellent cosmetic outcomes achieved, with minimal visible scarring and restored symmetry in the eyebrow and eyelid regions. The diverse patient demographic highlights the approach's effectiveness across different individuals.

Authors	Journal	No of Patients	Clinical Spectrum	Surgical Goal	Approach related Complications	Cosmetic Outcomes(Long term)
Raza et al, 2010	Min Inv Neurosurgery	4	Meningioma, Pituitary Adenoma, Langerhan Cell Histicocytosis	100% (3GTR, 1 biopsy)	1 CSF leakage (Orbitotomy)	Excellent, No facial injury, Alopecia, Puckering, Brow Assymety
Xie et al, 2014	IJCEM	3	Meningiomas	100% (3-GTR)	0, Two - Orbital apex syndrome. Due to tumor	Excellent, No facial injury, Alopecia, Puckering, Brow Assymety
Mao, Gordon et al, 2020	ONS	82	Aneurysms	100% (95% Obliteration)	8.3%, CSF leak, temporalis atrophy, visual blurring, partial oculomotor paresis	98% excellent to good, No facial injury, Alopecia, Puckering, Brow Assymety
Elnokaly et al, 2020	SNI	44	Meningiomas, Cranipharyngioma, Astrocytoma, Pituitary macroadenoma	100% (75% GTR)	6.80%	Excellent, No facial injury, Alopecia, Puckering, Brow Assymety
Dzhindzhikhadze et al, 2020	AJNS Plastic Reconstructive	15	Aneurysms 30, Tumors-10 Meningiomas, Aneurysms, Dural AVF, Orbital hemangioma	100%	13.3%(2) - Traction injury, cognitive issues	Excellent, No facial injury, Alopecia, Puckering, Brow Assymety
Morrison et al, 2023		20		100%	0	Excellent, No facial injury, Alopecia, Puckering, Brow Assymety
Sarkar et al, 2024	Current	15	Ant Skull Base Meningioma, Aneurysms, ACF floor defects, Fungal sinusitis, Craniopharyngioma, Pituitary macroadenoma	100% (Meningioma - 75% GTR, Complete occlusion of Aneurysm - 100%)	2 out of fifteen (Infection - 1, Frontalis weakness - temp)	Excellent, No facial injury, Alopecia, Puckering, Brow Assymety

Figure 9 (Table 2): Literature Review of Trans Eyelid Approach Outcomes

Review of various studies on the trans eyebrow approach, detailing the number of patients, clinical spectrum, surgical goals, approach-related complications, and long-term cosmetic outcomes. It summarizes the effectiveness and safety of the trans eyebrow approach across different studies, highlighting high rates of successful outcomes and minimal long-term cosmetic complications.

Figure 10: Utility of 3D Printing in Surgical Planning and Simulation

a) A 3D printed model of a patient's skull, showcasing the tumor (Refer to Figure 6a) and the adjacent anatomical structures allowing for precise pre-operative planning.

b) Close-up view of the 3D printed model with a simulated bony opening, highlighting the area to be accessed during surgery.

c) View through the bony opening in the 3D printed model, simulating a microscopic view and demonstrating the internal structures and the space available for surgical instruments.

d) Another perspective through the bony opening, providing a clear view of the simulated surgical pathway and target area.

It demonstrates the use of 3D printing technology to create accurate anatomical models for surgical planning, enhancing precision and reducing potential complications during actual procedures.